

ISic1125

I.Sicily inscription 1125

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Sicily

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140610

1. [— — — — — — — — ο]-
2. ὅτε τι πα[ρ]θε[νι]-
3. κο[— —]ΝΟΥ [— — —]
4. ΛΟ[— —]ΠΡΟΛ [— — —]
5. πένθος ἄλ [αστον — —]
6. η, σὺ δὲ [—]ΕΡΓ [— τὸν]
7. ἀεὶ χρ[όνον —]ΕΙ ὕ [— —]
8. ΗΠΡΟ[— —]ΕΙ [— — — —]
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492738

EDCS 39102282

PHI 140610

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0306 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5552

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